

BENEFITS OF EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES TO THE SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF SELECTED COLLEGE STUDENTS IN A PRIVATE INSTITUTION IN GUMACA, QUEZON

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Benefits of Extracurricular Activities to the Social Development of Selected College Students in a Private Institution in Gumaca, Quezon

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Abstract

The research study titled "Benefits of Extracurricular Activities to the Social Development of Selected College Students in a Private Institution in Gumaca, Quezon" employed a descriptive research design to study about the benefits of extracurricular activities, focusing on empathy skills, interpersonal skills, problem-solving skills, and leadership skills. Utilizing a survey questionnaire as the primary data collection tool, the study involved 80 college students as participants, selected through proportionate random sampling. Data analysis included the use of frequency, percentage, mean, ranking, and Kruskal Wallis H-test for statistical treatment. The study revealed that the majority of respondents were in the age range of 20-22 years old, with a predominance of female participants. Notably, forty five percent of the respondents were associated with the BSBA department. The average mean of 4.16, interpreted as Moderately Agree, indicated agreement on empathy skills. Similarly, the average mean of 4.18, interpreted as Moderately Agree, indicated agreement on interpersonal skills. The average mean of 4.084, interpreted as Moderately Agree, indicated agreement on problem solving skills. Lastly, the average mean of 4.082, interpreted as Moderately Agree, indicated agreement on leadership skills. Additionally, the Kruskal Wallis H-test results rejected all null hypotheses related to age, sex, and department, suggesting a significant difference in the perceived benefits of extracurricular activities among respondents when grouped according to their profiles.

Keywords: *empathy skills, extracurricular activities, interpersonal skills, leadership skills, problem solving skills*

Introduction

There are different kinds of events that can capture your interest. Within the school campus, you may find yourself lack in certain subjects or short of confidence in oral presentations. It is important to recognize that each student possesses unique strengths and weaknesses, allowing people to excel in different areas. If you want to learn more and do better, engaging in extracurricular activities presents a different kind of opportunities. Extracurricular activities consist of different range of activities, including sports, music, theater, debate, student leadership, academic writing, and clubs. These activities help you grow and learn new skills, letting you focus on what you want to get good at. Are you among those students who wants to develop talents outside of school? Do you possess a love for sports, the arts, poster making, or engaging in brainstorming? These extracurricular activities are a great way to learn new things and make yourself grow, and to connect with peers and others.

Participating in extracurricular activities has been shown to play an important role in a student's college life and career development. It not only allows students to apply the knowledge they learn in the classroom to real life situations but also helps them develop important skills. Extracurricular Activities enable students to gain real experience and enhance their ability to apply classroom knowledge. (Rubin, Bomer et, al. 2002) conducted a study on business students and found that those who participated in Extracurricular Activities show higher social skills. They suggested that extracurricular involvement is associated with stronger communication, decision-making, and teamwork skills. Similarly, (Rynes, Trank et al. 2003) also found that students who engaged in Extracurricular Activities show leadership and interpersonal skills. Extracurricular Activities have a positive impact on social skills such as interpersonal skills, teamwork skills, and communication skills, all of which contribute to future success. (Wood et, al. 2011).

This study helps people find their interests and what they want to improve for themselves. It shows how joining clubs and activities helps students make friends and associate with others and grow as people. It encourages trying new things outside of school, things you enjoy and want to get better at. Doing these activities helps you grow as a person and learn new skills that you can use in the future.

Research Questions

This study determined the benefits of extracurricular activities to the social development of selected college students in a private institution in Gumaca, Quezon S.Y 2023-2024. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex; and
 - 1.3. department?
2. What are the benefits of extracurricular activities to the social development of selected college student in terms of:
 - 2.1. empathy skills;
 - 2.2. leadership skills;
 - 2.3. problem solving skills; and

- 2.4. interpersonal skills?
3. Is there any significant difference on the perception about the benefits of extracurricular activities to the development of selected college students in a private institution in Gumaca, Quezon when the respondents are grouped according to profile?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used descriptive survey method to collect data to benefits of extracurricular activities to the social development of selected college students in Eastern Quezon College Inc. in Gumaca, Quezon. The researcher used survey questionnaire as an instrument. Based on the survey's result the researcher determined the details of the study. According to Manuel and Medel (1998) descriptive method involves description, recording, analysis and interpretation of the present nature, composition, or process of phenomena.

Respondents

The researcher selected 80 students through proportionate random sampling who are enrolled in Eastern Quezon College in the S.Y 2023-2024 and the benefits of extracurricular activities to the social development of selected college students was the focus of the study. The respondents were composed of 30 male and 50 female college students with the total of 80 students. According to Crossman (2020) In proportionate sampling, the sample size of each stratum is equal to the subgroup's proportion in the population as a whole.

Instrument

The researcher prepared a researcher-made questionnaire in which were validated by two experts. Part I of the questionnaire included the profile of the respondents. Part II of the questionnaire consisted of the benefits of extracurricular activities using Likert scale of; 5 – Strongly Agree (SA), 4 – Agree (A), 3 – Moderately Agree (MA), 2 – Disagree (D) and 1 – Strongly Disagree (SD) as perceived by the selected college students in a private school in Gumaca, Quezon.

To test the internal consistency of the questionnaire using Cronbach's Alpha, a pilot testing was conducted at SLSU with 12 respondents.

After the computation, the result was 0.90 and above which is interpreted as acceptable. This means that there is an internal consistency in the prepared research instrument.

Procedure

Prior to the conduct of the study, the researcher sent a letter to the department heads of the college of administration. Upon being approved, the researcher administered the instrument to the target respondents.

In administering the questionnaire, the researcher used the time allotted for vacant time to avoid distraction of class discussion. The student response was given enough time to answer the questions. After data gathering, the researcher collected them for tallying the scores and to apply the statistical treatment to be used in the study.

The descriptive research method using likert scale was used to rate the benefits of extracurricular to the social development of selected college students. Data were gathered through "Proportionate random sampling" both male and female of selected college student in Eastern Quezon College in Gumaca, Quezon were selected to fill the questionnaire. Data were gathered through face-to-face survey following the safety health protocols to prevent of the virus.

Data Analysis

In this study, the researcher used statistical measures to treat the collected data. All the data were carefully read and examined for analysis. They were tallied and entered a master list of the data collection sheet. Percentage and Frequency was used to interpret the profile of the respondents.

To get the weighted mean to describe the items in the indicators, the researcher used the formula (Calmorin, 2007; 116-118). To test the significant difference of three or more means, the researcher used the Kruskal-Wallis for non-parametric test.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the analysis and interpretation of the data. All the data gathered were presented here in tabulated form with corresponding interpretation. The first part described the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, and department The second part is the benefits of extracurricular activities to the social development of selected college students in a private institution in Gumaca, Quezon.

Table 1 displays the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to their age groups. The data reveals that the largest proportion of participants, constituting 39%, fall within the 20-22 age bracket. Following this, 27% of respondents are aged 23-24, while 23% belong to the 17-19 age range. Notably, only 11% of respondents are 25 years old and above, indicating a lower representation in this older age category

Table 1. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
17-19 years old	18	23
20-22 years old	31	39
23-24 years old	22	27
25 years old and above	9	11
Total	80	100

As mentioned by Laraib et al. (2020) the data gathered from 400 students reveals that 76% of the participants fall within the 18 to 22 age group, with the remaining 24% belonging to the 23 and above age group. This breakdown suggests a potential variation in respondent perceptions based on age groups.

The distribution of respondents across various age groups, as depicted in Table 1, emphasizes the importance of considering age diversity in research analysis and interpretation. The majority of participants in the 20-22 age bracket, followed by those aged 23-24 and 17-19, suggests a concentration of younger individuals in the study sample. This demographic profile based on age emphasizes the need to recognize potential variations in respondent perceptions based on age groups. The study by Laraib et al. (2020) further stated this point by revealing a significant proportion of participants in the 18 to 22 age group compared to older age groups. Understanding how age influences perspectives and behaviors is important for tailoring interventions and strategies to address the unique needs of different age cohorts. By acknowledging age-related differences in research design and intervention development, researchers can ensure the relevance and effectiveness of their approaches across diverse age demographics.

Table 2. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Male	30	37
Female	50	63
Total	80	100

In Table 2, the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents by gender are presented, highlighting that the majority of college participants are female, comprising 63% of the sample. In contrast, male respondents make up 37% of the total, indicating a lower representation of males compared to females in the study group.

Table 2 displays the proportion and distribution of male and female respondents in the study, with females representing the majority at 63%, while males comprised 37% of the total. This is consistent with previous research conducted by Fredericks & Essles (2013) in a similar context, which also found a higher proportion of female participants compared to males.

The distribution of respondents by gender, as outlined in Table 2, reveals a notable gender disparity within the study sample, with female participants accounting for 63% and male participants representing 37% of the total. This imbalance raises implications for data interpretation, generalizability of findings, and the understanding of gender-specific perspectives. The consistent trend of higher female representation, as indicated by previous research by Fredericks & Essles (2013), emphasizes the need for a gender-sensitive approach in analysis to avoid potential biases and ensure comprehensive opinions. Understanding the impact of gender on responses and behaviors is important for drawing conclusions that account for different gender perspectives. The gender distribution emphasizes the necessity of promoting opportunity in research recruitment to capture a balanced representation of genders and enhance the validity and relevance of study outcomes. By acknowledging and addressing gender disparities in research samples, researchers can conduct more thorough gender-sensitive analyses, identify gender-specific trends, and develop tailored interventions that cater to the needs of all gender groups.

Table 3. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Sex*

<i>Department</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
BSED	16	20
BSBA	36	45
AB	15	19
BEED	13	16
Total	80	100

In Table 3, the frequency and percentage distribution of participants based on their respective departments are presented. The data illustrates that the majority of respondents, constituting 45%, are affiliated with the BSBA department. Additionally, 20% of the participants are from the BSED department, while 19% belong to the AB department. The remaining 16% of respondents are associated with the BEED department, indicating a relatively smaller representation in this specific department category.

The moderate benefits in communication and self-promotion skills across all activities may contribute to the overall employability of BSBA students. However, the limited impact on time management skills implies that BSBA students may need to focus on developing

this skill through alternative means to enhance their employability prospects. (Lau et al. 2014).

The implications of the results from Table 3 emphasize the significance of departmental diversity in research analysis, the potential influence of departmental backgrounds on study outcomes, and the importance of considering department-specific insights for tailored interventions and broader generalizability.

Table 4. Respondents Assessment on the Perceived Benefits of Extracurricular activities to the Social Development of Selected College Students in a Private Institution in Gumaca, Quezon in terms of Empathy Skills

Indicator	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. gives me a chance to learn about others.	4.08	Moderately Agree
2. fosters my consideration for others' feelings and viewpoints.	4.15	Moderately Agree
3. leads me to interact with people who have unique, experiences, cultures, and perspectives.	4.18	Moderately Agree
4. allows me to see the world through their eyes, fostering a deeper sense of empathy and compassion.	4.11	Moderately Agree
5. Offers me an incredible opportunity to develop understanding towards individuals from diverse background.	4.27	Strongly Agree
Average Mean	4.16	Moderately Agree

Legend: Strongly Disagree (1.00-1.80), Disagree (1.81-2.60), Agree (2.61-3.40), Moderately Agree (3.41-4.20), Strongly Agree (4.21-5.00)

Table 4 presents the benefits of extracurricular activities on the social development of selected college students in terms of empathy skills. The highest mean score is observed in indicator number 5, "Offers me an incredible opportunity to develop understanding towards individuals from diverse backgrounds," with an average of 4.27, indicating a strong agreement among respondents. In contrast, the lowest mean score is found in indicator number 1, "Gives me a chance to learn about others," with an average of 3.41, reflecting a moderate level of agreement among participants.

The study's results indicate that integrating soft skills and extracurricular activities into the academic environment can contribute to students' holistic development, including their ability to empathize and connect with individuals from different backgrounds. By recognizing the importance of soft skills and extracurricular activities in shaping students' academic achievement, life satisfaction, and interpersonal skills, the study emphasize the importance of promoting empathy and understanding towards others as part of a comprehensive approach to education. The emphasis on soft skills and their positive impact on various aspects of students' academic and personal well-being suggests that developing empathy, understanding, and respect for individuals from different backgrounds is important. By fostering soft skills through activities like extracurricular involvement, students have the opportunity to enhance their empathy skills and broaden their understanding of others' perspectives and experiences. (Feraco et al. 2023)

The results from Table 4 emphasize the significant benefits of extracurricular activities on the social development of college students, particularly in terms of empathy skills. The strong agreement among respondents regarding the opportunity to develop understanding towards individuals from different background emphasizes the positive impact of such activities on fostering empathy and connection. However, the lower level of agreement in providing opportunities to learn about others suggests an area for improvement in facilitating different learning experiences through extracurricular involvement.

Table 5. Respondents Assessment on the Perceived Benefits of Extracurricular activities to the Social Development of Selected College Students in a Private Institution in Gumaca, Quezon in terms of Interpersonal Skills

Indicator	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. enhances my ability to listen attentively and understand others.	4.18	Moderately Agree
2. helps me to understand and use nonverbal and verbal cues effectively.	4.15	Moderately Agree
3. helps me to resolve conflicts and contribute to building positive relationship with peers.	4.12	Moderately Agree
4. gives me an opportunity to practice expressing my thoughts and ideas in a clear and concise manner.	4.15	Moderately Agree
5. provides me an opportunity to practice active listening and understand different perspectives.	4.32	Strongly Agree
Average Mean	4.18	Moderately Agree

Legend: Strongly Disagree (1.00-1.80), Disagree (1.81-2.60), Agree (2.61-3.40), Moderately Agree (3.41-4.20), Strongly Agree (4.21-5.00)

Table 5 illustrates the benefits of extracurricular activities on the social development of selected college students concerning empathy skills. The highest mean score is observed in indicator number 5, "Provides me an opportunity to practice active listening and understand different perspectives," with an average of 4.32, indicating a strong agreement among respondents. Conversely, the lowest mean score is found in indicator number 3, "Helps me to resolve conflicts and contribute to building positive relationships with peers," with an average of 4.12, reflecting a moderate level of agreement among participants.

The study findings align closely with the idea of improved interpersonal skills through Extracurricular activities. By participating in these activities, students likely had the opportunity to interact with peers from different backgrounds, engage in collaborative tasks, and interpret various challenges together. This exposure would have fostered active listening, understanding others' perspectives, and communication skills, contributing to the overall development of their interpersonal competencies. The study's confirmation that ECAs promote the gain of interpersonal skills and professional behaviors among medical students emphasizes how such activities can enhance students' ability to listen attentively and understand others. The nature of ECAs likely provided an opportunity for students to practice

effective communication, empathy, and respectful interaction, ultimately contributing to their holistic development and readiness for professional settings. (Jamal, 2014)

Table 6. Respondents Assessment on the Perceived Benefits of Extracurricular activities to the Social Development of Selected College Students in a Private Institution in Gumaca, Quezon in terms of Problem-Solving Skills

Indicator	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. leads me to come up with unique approaches to address challenges.	4.07	Moderately Agree
2. demonstrates my ability to contribute ideas, collaborate with others, and think critically to find solutions.	4.15	Moderately Agree
3. makes me become flexible and can adjust my strategies when faced with obstacles.	4.05	Moderately Agree
4. leads me to think creatively and can think outside the box.	4.08	Moderately Agree
5. can help me weigh the pros and cons, analyze different alternatives, and make decisions.	4.07	Moderately Agree
Average Mean	4.084	Moderately Agree

Legend: Strongly Disagree (1.00-1.80), Disagree (1.81-2.60), Agree (2.61-3.40), Moderately Agree (3.41-4.20), Strongly Agree (4.21-5.00)

Table 6 outlines the benefits of extracurricular activities on the social development of selected college students in terms of problem-solving skills. The indicator with the highest mean score is number 2, "Demonstrates my ability to contribute ideas, collaborate with others, and think critically to find solutions," with an average of 4.15, indicating a moderate level of agreement among respondents. On the other hand, the lowest mean score is observed in indicator number 3, "Makes me become flexible and can adjust my strategies when faced with obstacles," with an average of 4.05, also reflecting a moderate level of agreement among the participants.

The study's findings reveal the significant role of positive peer relationships in enhancing academic engagement and participation in extracurricular activities. The influence of friends, peer support, and social experiences like peer rejection and bullying highlights how peer interactions can shape students' abilities to contribute ideas, collaborate with others, and think critically. The examination of friend selection, friendship quality, and the type of support received further emphasizes the important role of peer relationships in developing academic engagement and involvement in school activities (Juvonen et al. 2012). The study's viewpoint into the impact of peer relationships on student motivation and engagement closely align with indicators related to contributing ideas, collaboration, and critical thinking.

The results from Table 6 shed light on the benefits of extracurricular activities on the social development of college students, particularly in terms of problem-solving skills. The moderate level of agreement among respondents in indicators such as contributing ideas, collaborating with others, and thinking critically to find solutions demonstrates the positive influence of these activities on enhancing problem-solving abilities. However, the slightly lower agreement in indicators related to flexibility and adjusting strategies in the face of obstacles suggests an area for potential growth in developing problem-solving skills through extracurricular engagement.

Table 7. Respondents Assessment on the Perceived Benefits of Extracurricular activities to the Social Development of Selected College Students in a Private Institution in Gumaca, Quezon in terms of Leadership Skills

Indicator	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. provides me with opportunities to inspire and motivates others.	4.26	Strongly Agree
2. helps me learn how to effectively convey ideas, actively listen, and ensure everyone is on the same page.	4.16	Moderately Agree
3. has given me the chance to make tough decision.	4.18	Moderately Agree
4. teach me to navigate through obstacles and lead my team towards success.	4.06	Moderately Agree
5. encourage me to push my team to their limits and strive for excellence.	3.75	Moderately Agree
Average Mean	4.08	Moderately Agree

Legend: Strongly Disagree (1.00-1.80), Disagree (1.81-2.60), Agree (2.61-3.40), Moderately Agree (3.41-4.20), Strongly Agree (4.21-5.00)

Table 7 presents the benefits of extracurricular activities on the social development of selected college students in terms of problem-solving skills. The indicator with the highest mean score is number 1, "Provides me with opportunities to inspire and motivate others," with an average of 4.26, indicating a strong agreement among respondents. Conversely, the lowest mean score is observed in indicator number 5, "Encourages me to push my team to their limits and strive for excellence," with an average of 3.75, reflecting a moderate level of agreement among the participants.

The findings suggest that schools offering a different range of extracurricular activities tend to have higher participation rates and better academic outcomes. This implies that students engaging in these activities not only benefit academically but also have the opportunity to inspire and motivate their peers through their involvement. The positive connection between activity availability, participation rates, and academic success links the importance of extracurricular engagement in fostering a supportive and inspiring school environment, the study's emphasis on the role of both school resources and student investment in extracurricular activities aligns with the understanding of inspiring and motivating others (Stearns & Glennie 2010).

Students actively participating in these activities not only enhance their own skills and academic performance but also serve as role models and sources of inspiration for their peers. Therefore, the study's insights into the impact of extracurricular activities on academic outcomes directly support the idea that such engagement provides an opportunities for students to inspire and motivate others within the school community.

Table 8. *Summary Table on the Perceived Benefits of Extracurricular to the Social Development of Selected College Students in a Private Institution in Gumaca, Quezon*

<i>Impact of using gadgets as tools for learning</i>	<i>Average Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
Empathy	4.16	Moderately Agree
Interpersonal	4.18	Moderately Agree
Problem Solving	4.084	Moderately Agree
Leadership	4.082	Moderately Agree
Average Mean	4.13	Moderately Agree

Legend: Strongly Disagree (1.00-1.80), Disagree (1.81-2.60), Agree (2.61-3.40), Moderately Agree (3.41-4.20), Strongly Agree (4.21-5.00)

Table 8 summarizes the benefits of extracurricular activities on the social development of selected college students by providing the average mean and corresponding verbal interpretation for four variables: empathy skills, interpersonal skills, problem-solving skills, and leadership. The mean for empathy skills was 4.16, indicating agreement, while the mean for interpersonal skills was 4.18. Additionally, the mean for problem-solving skills was 4.084, and the mean for leadership skills was 4.082.

These findings suggest that extracurricular activities have the most significant benefits on enhancing students' interpersonal skills compared to their leadership skills, problem-solving skills, and empathy skills. In relation to the study results where interpersonal skills have shown the highest mean among the four variables assessed, it is evident that participation in various activities, including sports, fine arts, and academic clubs, plays a significant role in shaping the interpersonal capabilities of individuals. While all extracurricular activities contribute positively to personality development and interpersonal skills, each type of activity offers a distinct profile in terms of skill enhancement and personal growth. This emphasizes the importance of recognizing the unique benefits that different extracurricular activities can offer in nurturing and strengthening interpersonal skills among participants. (Valeria & Oksana, 2015)

Table 9. *Significant Difference on the Perceived Benefits of Extracurricular Activities to the Social development Of Selected College Students in terms of when grouped according to respondents' Age*

<i>Groups</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Median</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>P - value</i>	<i>Significant Level</i>	<i>Decision</i>
17-19 y/o	18	4	3	0.001	0.05	Reject Ho
20-22y/0	31	4.05				
23-24 y/o	22	4.23				
25 y/o and above	9	4.10				

Table 9 displays that the calculated P-value is 0.001. At a significance level of 0.05 and 3 degrees of freedom, the critical value is 7.815. As the calculated H-value is higher than the critical value, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is noteworthy difference in the responses of students when classified according to age, indicating that students aged 17-19, 20-22, 23-24, and 25 years old and above have a different perception on the benefits of extracurricular activities in terms of age.

The research data collected from 400 students shows that 76% of the participants are in the age group of 18 to 22, while 24% belong to the age group of 23 and above. This distribution indicates a significant difference in respondent perceptions when the participants are grouped by age. The distinct age groups may have diverse experiences, perspectives, and attitudes, suggesting that age could be a significant factor influencing the perceptions and responses of the respondents in the study (Laraib et al. 2020).

Table 10. *Significant Difference on the Perceived Benefits of Extracurricular Activities to the Social development Of Selected College Students in terms of when grouped according to respondents' Sex*

<i>Groups</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Median</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>P - value</i>	<i>Significant Level</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Male	30	4.13	1	0.0001	0.05	Reject Ho
Female	50	4.1				

According to Table 10, the determination of whether there is a significant difference on the perceived benefits of extracurricular activities based on the respondents' gender shows that the P-value is 0.0001. This value is higher than the critical value of 3.841 at a significance level of 0.05 and with 1 degree of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, when a P- value of 0.0001 indicating that there is a significant difference between the responses of male and female of college students.

The data collected from 400 students reveals a notable difference in respondent perceptions when grouped by sex. With 62% of the participants being female and 38% male, the unequal distribution of sexes in the study sample suggests that there may be different perspectives and responses based on gender. This difference in male and female representation indicates a influence on the perceptions and outcomes of the research, stating the significance of considering sex as a factor in analyzing the data and drawing conclusions. (Laraib et al. 2020).

The results from Table 10 reveal a significant difference in the perceived benefits of extracurricular activities based on the gender of college students, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This finding suggests that male and female students hold different perceptions and experiences regarding the benefits derived from participating in extracurricular activities. The unequal distribution of

sexes in the study sample, with a higher representation of females, indicates the influence of gender on these perceptions and outcomes. Understanding these gender-related differences is essential for targeting extracurricular programs to meet the diverse needs and preferences of male and female students, enhancing their overall engagement and satisfaction with these activities.

Table 11. *Significant Difference on the Perceived Benefits of Extracurricular Activities to the Social development of Selected College Students in terms of when grouped according to respondents' department*

<i>Groups</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Median</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>P - value</i>	<i>Significant Level</i>	<i>Decision</i>
BSED	16	4.1	3	0.002	0.05	Reject Ho
BSBA	36	4.13				
AB	15	4.15				
BEED	13	4.05				

Table 11 displays the calculated P-value is 0.002. At a significance level of 0.05 and 3 degrees of freedom, the critical value is 7.815. As the calculated H-value is higher than the critical value. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, when a P- value of 0.002 indicates that there is a significant difference between the responses of college students by department.

The findings of the study indicate that various types of extra-curricular activities can have unequal effects on the employability of graduating college students. Specifically, leadership skills were most positively influenced by participation in sports clubs, while creativity skills were most enhanced by involvement in music clubs. Communication and self-promotion skills showed moderate benefits from all extracurricular activities. However, time management skills did not significantly benefit from participation in extra-curricular activities.

In the context of BSBA students, who constituted the majority of the study's respondents, these results suggest that their employability outcomes may be influenced differently compared to students from other departments. The emphasis on leadership skills from sports clubs and creativity skills from music clubs may have a significant impact on BSBA students' readiness for the job market. Additionally, the moderate benefits in communication and self-promotion skills across all activities may contribute to the overall employability of BSBA students. However, the limited impact on time management skills implies that BSBA students may need to focus on developing this skill through alternative means to enhance their employability prospects. (Iau et al. 2014)

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are derived:

The majority of respondents are female and fall within the age range of 20-22 years old, indicating a specific demographic composition in the study sample

The researcher's conclusion suggests that the learner-respondents possess an awareness of the advantages of engaging in extracurricular activities for their social development, despite a potential lack of diverse perspectives observed in the study findings.

The study findings show a moderate level of agreement among students about the social benefits of extracurricular activities. Further research is needed to identify potential limitations.

The analysis of respondent profiles revealed significant differences in learners' perceptions of the benefits of extracurricular activities for their social development. The varying perspectives among respondents when categorized based on their profiles influence of individual characteristics on how extracurricular activities are perceived in enhancing social development.

Based on the findings and conclusion the researcher made the following recommendations:

For the Administrator, to ensure students' involvement, provide a wide variety of extracurricular activities that will suit different interests and abilities.

For the Parents, may encourage the child to participate in extracurricular activities that align with their interests and passions to support their social development and overall well-being.

To the Teachers, may acknowledge and promote the benefits of extracurricular activities on student social development in addition to academic achievements.

To the Students, may explore and participate in a variety of extracurricular activities to discover interests, develop skills, and enhance social development/

To the Future researchers may conduct other studies using different variables to explore and gain a deeper understanding about the benefits of extracurricular activities to the social development of the students.

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